

ADAPTiCARE for Students: Expert Judgment of an Artificial Intelligence–Assisted Career Counseling Model to Enhance Career Adaptability Using Many Facet Rasch Measurement

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Abstract

This study aimed to validate ADAPTiCARE, an artificial intelligence assisted career counseling model designed to enhance students' career adaptability. The model is structured to support students across the four core dimensions of career adaptability, namely concern, control, curiosity, and confidence, by utilizing AI features such as a chatbot interface and automated analysis. The validation process involved expert judgment and psychometric evaluation using the Many Facet Rasch Measurement Model (MFRM). Four expert raters from the guidance and counseling and educational technology field evaluated the ADAPTiCARE model based on indicators of relevance, clarity, and usability. A rubric-based assessment instrument was used to guide the assessments. Data analysis used the Multifaceted Rasch Measurement Model to assess the consistency of expert assessments, the difficulty level of each indicator, and the relative severity of each rater.

The analysis indicated that the model items generally conformed to the MFRM, with values of agreement and completeness falling within acceptable ranges. Raters demonstrated moderate consistency, with a fair agreement index indicating that 62.5% of similar ratings would be repeated under identical conditions. One rater was identified as slightly more severe than the others, but all were within acceptable severity ranges. The model demonstrated strong reliability (0.95) and reasonable mean ratings across indicators. These findings confirm that ADAPTiCARE is a valid and feasible AI-assisted model for improving career adaptation in students. Expert feedback indicates the model's potential to support adaptive career behaviors through AI-based personalized guidance. Further development is recommended for implementation at the school level, followed by a longitudinal study to assess its practical impact.

Keywords: *artificial intelligence, career adaptation, career counseling, expert validation, many facet rasch measurement*